

‘River’ as a metaphor of Resistance: A Study of *River of Stories* in Environmental Context

Malabika Sinha,
Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
Ananda Chandra College of Commerce,
DBC Road, Jalpaiguri, India.

Abstract: *Eco criticism refers to the intrinsic relationship between human and nature and how literature responds towards environmental degradation, climate change, anthropocentric approach and how our planet is severely affected that results in the imbalance of biodiversity and ecological disruptions. In an Anthropocene era, materialistic pursuits ultimately lead to ecological degradation, displacement, ill-effect on the lives of indigenous community. Orijit Sen is a pioneering figure and cultural critique who through his visual art and storytelling technique creates a graphic narrative that contests prevailing discourse of ‘development’. River of Stories is a seminal text of Sen that challenges the state-imposed decision for the sake of development within the graphic realm. This paper will try to analyze ecocritical perspectives, the intertwined relationship between human and nature, how Sen projects Anthropocene approaches in this graphic novel as well as building of dam on the river Rewa which creates a negative impact on the lives of indigenous people who are closely linked with the river and the brilliant synthesis of myth, folktale, environmental degradation, ecological awareness and the resistance of indigenous communities whose lives are changed for the sake of development and this paper also highlights the relevance of this graphic novel in present context of environmental as well as global crisis and sustainable development for all.*

Keywords: ecocriticism, capitalism, ecological awareness, oral tradition, resistance

Orijit Sen's *River of Stories* is considered as a first graphic novel published in 1994 set against the backdrop of the Narmada Bachao Andolan, a social movement. The visual storytelling technique projects a critique of the construction of Narmada dam, the much debated issue that creates uproar as this project has far-reaching impact on environment and the lives of the indigenous people. Eco criticism refers to the intrinsic relationship between human and nature and how literature responds towards environmental degradation, climate change, anthropocentric approach and how our planet is severely affected that results in the imbalance of biodiversity and ecological disruptions. In an Anthropocene era, materialistic pursuits ultimately lead to ecological degradation, displacement, ill-effect on the lives of indigenous community. Orijit Sen is a pioneering figure and cultural critique who through his visual art and storytelling technique creates a graphic narrative that contests prevailing discourse of 'development'. *River of Stories* is a seminal text of Sen that challenges the state-imposed decision for the sake of development within the graphic realm. This paper will try to analyze ecocritical perspectives, the intertwined relationship between human and nature, how Sen projects Anthropocene approaches in this graphic novel as well as building of dam on the river Rewa which creates a negative impact on the lives of indigenous people who are closely linked with the river and the brilliant synthesis of myth, folktale, environmental degradation, ecological awareness and the resistance of indigenous communities whose lives are changed for the sake of development and this paper also highlights the relevance of this graphic novel in present context of environmental as well as global crisis and sustainable development for all.

Ecocritical works share a common theme that most of the global catastrophes are the consequences of human activities and we are at the threshold of environmental limits. As Donald Worster comments:

We are facing a global crisis today, not because of how ecosystems function but rather because of how our ethical systems function. Getting through the crisis requires understanding our impact on nature as precisely as possible, but even more, it requires understanding those ethical systems and using that understanding to reform them. Historians, along with literary scholars, anthropologists, and philosophers, cannot do the reforming, of course, but they can help with the understanding. (27)

Ecocriticism is the study of the relationship between literature and the environment and it has an earth centered approach to literary studies. The term was first coined by William Ruckert in 1978 in his essay entitled “Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism” which refers to the application of ecology and ecological concepts to the study of literature. The ecological criticism shares a fundamental notion:

Despite the broad scope of inquiry and disparate levels of sophistication, all ecological criticism shares the fundamental premise that human culture is connected to the physical world, affecting it and affected by it. Ecocriticism takes as its subject the interconnections between nature and culture, specifically the cultural artifacts of language and literature. As a critical stance, it has one foot in literature and the other on land; as a theoretical discourse, it negotiates between the human and the nonhuman.

Ecocriticism can be further characterized by distinguishing it from other critical approaches. Literary theory, in general, examines the relations between writers, texts, and the world. In most literary theory “the world” is synonymous with society – the social sphere. Ecocriticism expands the notion of “the world” to include the entire ecosphere. If we agree with Barry Commoner's first law of ecology, “Everything is connected to everything else,” we must conclude that literature does not float above the material world in some aesthetic ether, but, rather, plays a part in an immensely complex global system, in which energy, matter, and *ideas* interact. (*Glotfelty and Fromm xix*)

Hydrocolonialism is a term that refers to destructive effects on ecosystem but not for any particular place rather it is transregional. As Pramod K. Nayar comments in this respect:

In their emphasis on resistance, protest and resilience, whether in the form of *River of Stories*' representation of the anti-dam campaign or in Bhimayana's representation of Ambedkar as a reviving elixir of life, water is also the reason for insurgency and activism. The (re)turn to myth in *Finding My Way, Water and River of Stories* even offers up a different mythos to the dominant urban one of scarcity, regulation and commodification – one in which there is a greater respect and dependency that mark the human-nature relationship. Invoking myth, history, legends and stories conjoins the contemporary practices of development – which are instantiations of humanity's colonization of nature – with precolonial (but not necessarily romanticized) histories of the people, especially forest dwellers and the tribals. Within these histories, the author-artists locate a different worldview, even a means of resistance and rebellion. (63)

River of Stories as the metaphor of resistance:

In the context of anthropocentric approaches and sustainable development, this graphic novel narrates capitalist and materialistic pursuits. The story is about 'development' and the consequences caused by building a dam on the river Rewa. It shadows the story of building Sardar Sarovar Dam on the Narmada river despite the protest against it. In the 'Forward' of *River of Stories* Arundhati Roy comments:

Today, almost three decades later, that story continues to be current, urgent and perhaps the most important story we need to hear and understand. As this new edition of *River of Stories* goes to press, the newspapers carry photographs and reports of what has happened to the Narmada. Downstream of the dam, the once mighty, ethereally beautiful river barely exists.

No longer does she rush to meet the sea.

No longer does the sea open its arms to greet her.

No longer does that unique estuary exist in which sweet water and the salty sea mingled to create a magical breeding place for fish and flora.

No longer do the tens of thousands of fisher folk whose livelihood she provided for – over generations – turn to her for sustenance.

Downstream of the dam, the Narmada is now a twenty-foot wide stream that you can wade across in the dry season. Cars are often parked on her dry, sandy riverbed.

River of Stories is a smooth pebble that you might stub your toe on as you wander among the parked cars. Bend down and pick it up. Cherish it. You might hear the murmur of rushing water.
(3)

Sen's graphic narrative is a ground breaking work that unfolds voices, stories, myths, their spirited resistance – and all are woven together making it a landmark that needs to be read and relevant also for today's generation. In the 'Forward' of *River of Stories*, Paul Gravett makes a comment:

Comics are narratives in fixed images. Their fixity cannot be overstated. In today's "attention economy", in our endless torrent of fast-breaking news coverage, a significant story can come to us live, moment-by-moment; but often in an instant it is gone and forgotten, replaced by the next story, and the next... The images and words in printed comics, however, do not go away. You can't swipe or scroll them out of sight and switch to something else, you can't click for them and jump to another report or website, you can't change channels. This is a real strength of the medium. These stories, these voices, these ideas, these questions persist –and they resist, and they insist. Orijit Sen's landmark work of graphic reportage is all the stronger for being in comics form, because he has fixed these events and

ideas into drawings and texts printed onto paper, for more and more people to learn from.

Twenty-five years later and more urgent than ever, they continue to flow with us into the future. (*Sen 5*)

The story is about river, the metaphor of fluidity of life and resistance. It tells the story of the tribal people, their exploitation, agonies, protest against injustice in the environmental context. The fluidity, the continuity of life capture the essence of the narrative:

This is the story of a river...

and the story itself is a river.

A river that welled up from

the deepest, oldest springs

of consciousness.

Flowing over the hills of experience

and forests of memory,

it carried with it coloured stones

of wisdom polished and rounded. (*Sen 12*)

The narrative covers the journey of a reporter Vishnu who uncovers the story within the story and the conflict between cultures – the ideologies of modernization in the postcolonial world and the socio, political critique highlighting numerous displaced individuals. Relku, who works at the house of Vishnu is a displaced and migrant worker leaving behind her native village and land for the sake of development, the building of a large dam over the river Rewa:

It was like a big snake, from whose belly emerged the traders from the bazar. Earlier, no bazar would have come into our

forest even by mistake. But the road changed that... They started by setting up small shops and businesses near the road... Slowly, they began to take over our land, sometimes even by force... One by one... so many lost their homes. We did not know that our turn would also come soon. (*Sen 24-25*)

Relku's journey from a happy family to a landless labourer reveals the exploitative methods of the civilized society and the representatives of it. Here, we find the role of Gupta who plays a negative role against her family; his words are against them who had all necessary papers and the *adhikaris* are on his side. An accident happened and a great fire devastated everything of her family:

I will never forget that time, Vishnubhai. One day we were happy cultivating our own land... living in a house my father and uncles had built with their own hands... and the next day we were on the way to Ballanpur to work as landless labourers... with no money and possessions. The rest of my family still lives there. But after I married, my husband found work in the city, and I left with him... My life is like a river, mother... And on it I float away to the big city. I hear the sirens of the factory, father... Calling, beckoning. I leave your world far behind... (*Sen 33*)

The narrative revolves around the environmental issues, ecological consciousness and the loss of biodiversity due to flawed development projects and the consequence leads to submerge of lands and displacement of numerous people:

According to official figures, the dam's reservoir will submerge land and forests, affecting about 100,000 people... Around 375 square kilometers of forest and farmland will go under water... Even if you add another lakh of people to be displaced by the irrigation canal network, it's still nothing compared to the benefits the project will bring. (*Sen 40*)

The building of the dam has the history of displacement of tribal communities. The oral tradition, myth, folklore and the issue of displacement are blended in an excellent way. They protest against injustice, they want to preserve the ecosystem of their place. Here, the legendary figure of Malgu Gayan and the myth associated with his name are heard. The belief is that Malgu's song now will be heard by all. The indigenous communities and their knowledge, oral tradition as well as their relation with Mother Nature – all are woven together:

They have many legends and songs about folk heroes who fought for their freedom. You'll hear some of those songs later. That same spirit of resistance is alive today, and it's growing... People know that their struggle against the dam is a fight against injustice, and they're determined to defend their land, their way of life, their identity. It's almost as though the legendary Malgu Gayan has picked up his rangai and begun to sing –calling out to his people to unite and rise up again! (*Sen 48-49*)

Sen gives importance to the indigenous knowledge of the villagers, how the farmers protect the catchment, plant right trees and crops to improve the quality of the soil, how they have their own method of harnessing water, old system of catching and storing water for future use and thus they enrich the environment. Their protest is cultural as well as spiritual protest emphasizing the preservation of nature and their age old beliefs, traditions and indigenous knowledge for the future generations. The marginalized communities raise their voice of protest against the hegemonic power structure. Nature posits an active and significant role in the artistic creation. But how modernization, urbanization, scientific development and technical advancement create a massive impact on the environment as well as on the marginalized sections are manifested in literature as we should not forget that literature can be instrumental by raising consciousness about the endangered environment and we are already at the threshold of global catastrophe:

The tradition of nature writing in English literature is a description or depiction of particular landscape or seasonal changes. It is generally considered that it is a kind of monologue, which remains alienated from the rest of the world. Literature always leads us away from the physical world and never back to it. In fact, in the last part of the 20th century, there has been a growing sense of discomfort in the academic world that critics have failed to respond to natural world and that they have failed to enter into a dialogue of natural diversity as manifested in the plurality of human culture. There is, therefore, a need to engage the creative writers, critics and audience in a dialogue keeping in view the natural, ethical, aesthetic and global perspectives of literature. (*Chandra and Das 11*)

Arundhati Roy, a renowned writer and social activist, reflects multidimensional issues like capitalism, influence of corporate world, globalization and state policies with negative consequences on the ordinary mass in her non-fiction book *An Ordinary Person's Guide to Empire*. The essay "The Road to Harsud" is about building the Narmada Sagar Dam and the adverse effects on human and non-human. Harsud, a seven hundred years old town in Madhya Pradesh, is submerged by the reservoir of Narmada Sagar Dam and a catastrophe leads to destruction of ecological balance and the loss of biodiversity of that place. The displacement causes a havoc impact on the lives of ordinary people:

In New Harsud there's no water, no sewage system, no shelter, no school, no hospital. Plots have been marked out like cells in a prison, with mud roads that criss-cross at right angles. They get water from a tanker. Sometimes they don't. There are no toilets and there is not a tree or a bush in sight for them to piss or shit behind. When the wind rises it takes the tin sheets with it. When it rains, the scorpions come out of the wet earth. Most important of all, there's no work in New Harsud. No means of earning a livelihood. (*Roy 258*)

In *The Nutmeg's Curse: Parables for a Planet in Crisis*, Amitav Ghosh reflects on the interconnected relationship between colonial

exploitations and ecological disruptions and how the present problem of climate change is deeply rooted with the history of power, exploitation, conflict and geopolitics. The colonial domination of the West over a large segment of the world posits a threat on the existence of others and creates a sense of vulnerability. The Bandanese Archipelago is a place of precious nutmegs. The commodification of nutmegs leads to violence, aggression, domination and extermination of the whole tribe by the Dutch. The capitalistic attitude and materialistic pursuits of the West leads to exploitation of native populations and the intrusion into the natural world. They perceive nature only as a resource and natural resource extraction causes devastating effects on the ecosystem and the balance in the biodiversity of the whole island is deeply affected:

Here, Ghosh refers to climate crisis and the adverse consequences upon the ordinary mass:

In other words, the phenomenon of climate change and the research that surrounds it have come to be almost totally identified with each other. Arguably, there exists no other sphere of contemporary life in which there is so great an overlap between a phenomenon and the credentialed literature that frames it. In discussions of the economy, for instance, it is not assumed that only economists or academic experts can speak of the subject. It is generally accepted that workers, shopkeepers, factory managers, stockbrokers, and others who have no acquaintance with the expert literature may have valid perspectives of their own.

Climate change is a much vaster phenomenon than the economy, yet the voices and perspectives of those who are affected by it – farmers, fisherfolk, migrants and so on – very rarely figure in the discussion. And when they do, it is usually merely as victims, whose voices fill the blanks in a script that has already been written by specialists. (148)

River of Stories is a powerful critique of materialistic and Anthropocentric approaches. By focusing on the issues of displacement, loss of cultural identity, this novel also reflects holistic approach to modern development and advocates inclusion of indigenous communities and their knowledge for sustainable development. This graphic novel challenges dominant paradigms, the mainstream discourse on modernization and development by centering on complex social, political and environmental issues:

River of Stories is about the struggles of the characters that occupy the foreground of its 500-odd panels, but their stories are told as much through the backgrounds, for at one level they are all about living, changing landscapes. As my Adivasi companions of the Narmada Valley might say: “You city folk will learn to live in peace with Mother Earth only when, like true children, you sit and listen to her stories.” And so Malgusings on... (Sen 75-76)

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